

Lee Kong Chian Research Fellowship

Three new research fellows awarded

The Lee Kong Chian Research Fellowship welcomes three new research fellows: Sharon Wong Wai Wee (Hong Kong), Tan Teng Phee (Malaysia) and Dr Noel Chia Kok Hwee (Singapore). They were awarded their fellowships by Judy Ng, Deputy Director, National Reference and Special Libraries on 12 January.

(From left):
Ms Angie Ng Gek Tee, witness for Dr Chia; Dr Chia; Dr Mahani Awang, witness for Ms Wong; Ms Wong; Mrs Kornphanat Tungkeunkunt, witness for Mr Tan, and Mr Tan.

Sharon Wong's research topic is "An Overview of the Cultural and Technological Interactions Between the Chinese and Mainland Southeast Asian Ceramics Industries During the Period 9th to 16th Centuries".

She says of herself:

"I chose to continue my study in Singapore for more than four years because I believe that Singapore is a hub of Southeast Asia. While I also realise that Hong Kong is a gateway to the south China region, both of these two places have provided me with the best research environments in the regions. My research at the National Library will focus on the cultural and technological interaction between the Chinese and Southeast Asian ceramic industries from the 9th to the 16th centuries. One of my favourite experiences was joining the archaeological dig in Phnom Kulen in Siem Reap, Cambodia. I had the experience of being brought closer to the daily life of Cambodians. Besides work, I like travelling, watching movies and drama, cycling, and spending my time in bookstores and museums."

Tan Teng Phee's research topic is "The Assassination of Henry Gurney and the case of the Tras New Village and the Malayan emergency".

He says of himself:

"Born in Kuantan, Pahang, Malaysia, I had lived in several different Chinese New Villages and these life experiences had inspired me to explore the history of Chinese New Villages for my doctoral research. I commenced my PhD programme at the Asia Research Centre, Murdoch University, Western Australia,

in April 2006. My doctoral thesis attempts to analyse the everyday lives of the Chinese New Villagers behind barbed wire, and how they responded to the British colonial government's coercive policies. During the course of the Lee Kong Chian Research Fellowship from January 2010 to July 2010, I will focus on the unique case of the Tras New Village and its links to the assassination of the High Commissioner of Malaya, Henry Gurney, in 1951. This micro-level study aims to analyse how the assassination of the high commissioner both implicated and changed the New Villagers' lives and circumstances in Tras, during the Malayan Emergency period."

Dr Noel Chia's research topic is "A Survey on the Growth of Imagination in Children's English Literature in Singapore: 1965 - 2005."

Dr Chia says of himself:

"I am a board-certified educational therapist registered with the Association of Educational Therapists, United States, as well as a board-certified special education professional registered with the American Academy of Special Education Professionals. Besides, I am a registered professional counsellor with the Australian Institute of Professional Counsellors. Currently, I am an assistant professor with the Early Childhood & Special Needs Education Academic Group at the National Institute of Education/Nanyang Technological University. I spend most of my free time reading and writing not only academic papers but also stories and poems for children. Together with my daughter, Grace, I love creating imaginary tales along the line of fantasy and science fiction. I like humour and enjoy cracking jokes to make myself look silly! I have always been passionate about promoting Singapore children's literature in English. Here I am ... on this Lee Kong Chian Research Fellowship to research on the topic closest to my heart: imagination in children's literature..."

The Lee Kong Chian Research Fellowship invites scholars, practitioners and librarians to undertake collection-related research and publish on the National Library of Singapore's donor and prized collections. The fellowship aims to position the National Library Board as the first stop for Asian collection services. It is open to both local and foreign applicants, who should preferably have an established record of achievement in their chosen field of research and the potential to excel further. For information on the Lee Kong Chian Research Fellowship, please contact the Administrator at:

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